

*Fue Sho – Electrofusion*

Garth Paine and Michael Atherton

This is a semi-improvised exploration of the world of the “old skool” — the fortepiano and the world of rock and roll — the electric guitar. Imbued with spirits, stretched into mellifluous timbres, this work seeks to place the old and new into the cauldron of post modern musical landscape, taking known reference points and recontextualising them through the use of the Capybara/Kyma engine controlled by a Wacom Tablet.